

Some New Discrete Inequalities of Opial and Lasota's Type

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Abstract

In this paper, we establish some new discrete inequalities of Opial and Lasota's type which reduce to some inequalities in [4].

Keywords: Hölder's inequality; Opial inequality; Lasota inequality; Forward difference operator; Backward difference operator.

1. Introduction

In this paper, we denote $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^N$ by a sequence of real numbers, the operators Δ and ∇ by $\Delta x_i = x_{i+1} - x_i$ and $\nabla x_i = x_i - x_{i-1}$, and $[\cdot]$ by the greatest integer function. The empty sums is taken to be 0.

In 1960, Opial [7] established the following important integral inequality:

Theorem A. Let $f(x) \in C^1[0, h]$ be such that $f(0) = f(h) = 0$, and $f(x) > 0$ in $(0, h)$. Then

$$\int_0^h |f(x)f'(x)|dx \leq \frac{h}{4} \int_0^h (f'(x))^2 dx, \quad (1.1)$$

where $\frac{h}{4}$ is the best possible.

The inequality (1.1) is known in the literature as Opial inequality. For some results which generalize, improve and extend this famous integral inequality (see [1]-[11]).

In [4], Lasota provided discrete versions of Opial inequality (1.1) about the forward difference operator as following:

Theorem B. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^N$ be a sequence of numbers, and $x_0 = x_N = 0$. Then, the following inequality holds

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i \Delta x_i| \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right] \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (\Delta x_i)^2. \quad (1.2)$$

If N is even, then the inequality (1.2) is sharp.

Also, we have the following three Theorems C-E (see [1]):

Theorem C. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^{\tau}$ be a sequence of numbers, and $x_0 = 0$. Then, the following inequality holds

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\tau-1} |x_i \Delta x_i| \leq \frac{\tau-1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-1} (\Delta x_i)^2. \quad (1.3)$$

Theorem D. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=\tau}^N$ be a sequence of numbers, and $x_N = 0$. Then, the following inequality holds

$$\sum_{i=\tau}^{N-1} |x_i \Delta x_i| \leq \frac{N-\tau+1}{2} \sum_{i=\tau}^{N-1} (\Delta x_i)^2. \quad (1.4)$$

Theorem E. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^{\tau}$ be a sequence of numbers, and $x_0 = 0$. Then, the following inequality holds

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\tau} |x_i \nabla x_i| \leq \frac{\tau+1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{\tau} (\nabla x_i)^2. \quad (1.5)$$

We shall establish some new results which are the generalizations of Theorems B-E.

2. Main Results

Throughout this section, let $m, n > 0$ and $c(m, n) = \frac{1}{m+n} \max\{m, n\}$.

We state and prove the following theorems:

Theorem 1. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1) l \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}. \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. Since $x_0 = 0$, we have the following identity

$$x_i = \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \Delta x_j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, l. \quad (2.2)$$

Hence the following inequality holds

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m \leq \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j| |\Delta x_i|^m \right]. \quad (2.3)$$

Using the inequality

$$\alpha \beta^m \leq \frac{1}{m+1} \alpha^{m+1} + \frac{m}{m+1} \beta^{m+1} (\alpha, \beta > 0) \quad (2.4)$$

and the definition of $c(m, 1)$, we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j| |\Delta x_i|^m \right] \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \left(\frac{|\Delta x_j|^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{m}{m+1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \right) \right] \\
 & \leq c(m, 1) \sum_{i=1}^l \left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j|^{m+1} + i |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \right) \\
 & = c(m, 1) \sum_{i=0}^l [(l-i) |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} + i |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}] \\
 & = c(m, 1) l \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Using the inequalities (2.3) and (2.5), we derive the inequality (2.1). This completes the proof.

Remark 1. In the inequality (2.1), let $m = 1$ and $l = \tau - 1$. Then the inequality (2.1) reduces to the inequality (1.3).

Theorem 2. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}| |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1) (l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}. \tag{2.6}$$

Proof. Since $x_0 = 0$, we have the following identity

$$x_{i+1} = \sum_{j=0}^i \Delta x_j, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, l-1. \tag{2.7}$$

Using the inequality (2.4), the identity (2.7) and the definition of $c(m, n)$, we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}| |\Delta x_i|^m & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left[\sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j| |\Delta x_i|^m \right] \\
 & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left[\sum_{j=0}^i \left(\frac{|\Delta x_j|^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{m}{m+1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \right) \right] \\
 & \leq c(m, 1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left(\sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j|^{m+1} + (i+1) |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= c(m, 1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} [(l-i)|\Delta x_i|^{m+1} + (i+1)|\Delta x_i|^{m+1}] \\
&= c(m, 1)(l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.6). This completes the proof.

Theorem 3. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=l+1}^N$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_N = 0$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1)(N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}. \quad (2.8)$$

Proof. Let $x_i = y_{N-i}$ where $i = l+1, l+2, \dots, N$. Then

$$\Delta x_i = -\Delta y_{N-i-1} \text{ and } y_0 = 0$$

where $i = l+1, l+2, \dots, N-1$. Using the inequality (2.6), we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-l-2} |y_{i+1}| |\Delta y_i|^m \\
&\leq c(m, 1)(N-l) \sum_{i=0}^{N-l-2} |\Delta y_i|^{m+1} \\
&= c(m, 1)(N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.8). This completes the proof.

Remark 2. In the inequality (2.8), let $m = 1$ and $l = \tau - 1$. Then the inequality (2.8) reduces to the inequality (1.4).

Theorem 4. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^N$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = x_N = 0$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1) \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right] \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right]$ is the Gaussian integer of $\frac{N+1}{2}$.

If N is even, then the inequality (2.9) is sharp.

Proof. (1) Let $l = \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right]$. Then $N-l \leq l$. Using the inequalities (2.1) and (2.8), we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m &= \sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m + \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i| |\Delta x_i|^m \\ &\leq c(m, 1) \left\{ l \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} + (N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \right\} \\ &\leq c(m, 1) l \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.9).

(2) Suppose $m = 1$ and N is even. Then $\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right] = \frac{N}{4}$. Let

$$x_i = \frac{1}{2}N - \left| i - \frac{1}{2}N \right| \quad (0 \leq i \leq N-1).$$

Then, we have

$$x_0 = x_N = 0, |\Delta x_i| = 1 \quad (0 \leq i \leq N-1),$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i \Delta x_i| = \frac{1}{4}N^2 \text{ and } \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^2 = N.$$

Hence, the equality holds in the inequality (2.9) and from which the inequality (2.9) is sharp. This completes the proof.

Remark 3. In the inequality (2.9), let $m = 1$. Then the inequality (2.9) reduces to the inequality (1.2).

Theorem 5. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0, n > 1$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1) l^n \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}. \quad (2.10)$$

Proof. Using the identity (2.2), the Hölder's inequality with indices $n/(n-1), n$, and the inequality

$$\alpha^n \beta^m \leq \frac{n}{m+n} \alpha^{m+n} + \frac{m}{m+n} \beta^{m+n} \leq c(m, n) (\alpha^{m+n} + \beta^{m+n}) \quad (2.11)$$

where $\alpha, \beta > 0$, we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \leq \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j| \right)^n |\Delta x_i|^m \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} 1 \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j|^n \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right]^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^l i^{n-1} \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&\leq l^{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^l \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} |\Delta x_j|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&\leq c(m, n) l^{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^l \left[\sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (|\Delta x_j|^{m+n} + |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}) \right] \\
&= c(m, n) l^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^l [(l-i)|\Delta x_i|^{m+n} + i|\Delta x_i|^{m+n}] \\
&= c(m, n) l^n \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.10). This completes the proof.

Remark 4. In the inequality (2.10), let $n \rightarrow 1^+$. Then the inequality (2.10) reduces to the inequality (2.1).

Theorem 6. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0, n > 1$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, n) l^{n-1} (l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}. \quad (2.12)$$

Proof. Using the identity (2.7), the Hölder's inequality with indices $n/(n-1), n$, and the inequality (2.11), we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}|^n |\Delta x_i|^m &\leq \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left[\left(\sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j| \right)^n |\Delta x_i|^m \right] \\
&\leq \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left[\left(\sum_{j=0}^i 1 \right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}} \left(\sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j|^n \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right]^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} (i+1)^{n-1} \sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&\leq l^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \sum_{j=0}^i |\Delta x_j|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \\
&\leq c(m, n) l^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} \left[\sum_{j=0}^i (|\Delta x_j|^{m+n} + |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= c(m, n)l^{n-1} \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} [(l-i)|\Delta x_i|^{m+n} + (i+1)|\Delta x_i|^{m+n}] \\
&= c(m, n)l^{n-1}(l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.12). This completes the proof.

Remark 5. In the inequality (2.12), let $n \rightarrow 1^+$. Then the inequality (2.12) reduces to the inequality (2.6).

Theorem 7. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=l+1}^N$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_N = 0, n > 1$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, n)(N-l-1)^{n-1}(N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}. \quad (2.13)$$

Proof. Let $x_i = y_{N-i}$ where $i = l+1, l+2, \dots, N$. Then

$$\Delta x_i = -\Delta y_{N-i-1} \text{ and } y_0 = 0$$

where $i = l+1, l+2, \dots, N-1$. Using the inequality (2.12), we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-l-2} |y_{i+1}|^n |\Delta y_i|^m \\
&\leq c(m, n)(N-l-1)^{n-1}(N-l) \sum_{i=0}^{N-l-2} |\Delta y_i|^{m+n} \\
&= c(m, n)(N-l-1)^{n-1}(N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.13). This completes the proof.

Remark 6. In the inequality (2.13), let $n \rightarrow 1^+$. Then the inequality (2.13) reduces to the inequality (2.8).

Theorem 8. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^N$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = x_N = 0, n > 1$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m \leq c(m, n) \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right]^n \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n}. \quad (2.14)$$

Proof. Let $l = \left[\frac{N+1}{2} \right]$. Then $N-l-1 \leq N-l \leq l$. Using the inequalities (2.10) and (2.13), we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m = \sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m + \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |x_i|^n |\Delta x_i|^m$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq c(m, n) \left[l^n \sum_{i=0}^l |\Delta x_i|^{m+n} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (N-l-1)^{n-1} (N-l) \sum_{i=l+1}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n} \right] \\ &\leq c(m, n) l^n \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n} \end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.14). This completes the proof.

Under the conditions of Theorems 2 and 6, we have the following corollaries and remarks.

Corollary 1. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\nabla x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1)(l+1) \sum_{i=1}^l |\nabla x_i|^{m+1}. \quad (2.15)$$

Proof. Since

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\nabla x_i|^m = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}| |\Delta x_i|^m,$$

it follows from the inequality (2.6) that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^l |x_i| |\nabla x_i|^m &\leq c(m, 1)(l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+1} \\ &= c(m, 1)(l+1) \sum_{i=1}^l |\nabla x_i|^{m+1} \end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.15). This completes the proof.

Remark 7. In the inequality (2.15), let $m = 1$ and $l = \tau$. Then the inequality (2.15) reduces to the inequality (1.5).

Corollary 2. Let $\{x_i\}_{i=0}^l$ be a sequence of real numbers with $x_0 = 0, n > 1$. Then we have the following inequality

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\nabla x_i|^m \leq c(m, 1)(l+1)^n \sum_{i=1}^l |\nabla x_i|^{m+n}. \quad (2.16)$$

Proof. Since

$$\sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\nabla x_i|^m = \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |x_{i+1}|^n |\Delta x_i|^m,$$

it follows from the inequality (2.12) that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^l |x_i|^n |\nabla x_i|^m &\leq c(m, n) l^{n-1} (l+1) \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n} \\ &\leq c(m, n) (l+1)^n \sum_{i=0}^{l-1} |\Delta x_i|^{m+n} \\ &= c(m, n) (l+1)^n \sum_{i=1}^l |\nabla x_i|^{m+n} \end{aligned}$$

which is the inequality (2.16). This completes the proof.

Remark 8. For $x_i = i, 0 \leq i \leq l$ in the inequality (2.16), we note that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^l i^n &\leq c(m, n) (l+1)^n l \\ &< \max\{m, n\} \frac{(l+1)^{n+1} - 1}{n+1} \\ &< \max\{m, n\} \int_1^{l+1} t^n dt, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that the inequality (2.16) gives a better estimate than that obtained by simply comparing areas. Moreover, for $n \rightarrow 1^+$, this gives the well-known identity $\sum_{i=1}^l i = l(l+1)/2$.

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